

Nonlinear control for an optimized grid connection system of renewable energy resources

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ABSTRACT

This paper proposes an integral backstepping based nonlinear control strategy for a grid connected wind-photovoltaic hybrid system. The proposed control strategy aims at extracting the maximum power available while respecting the grid connection standards. The proposed system has a reduced number of power electronic converters, thereby ensuring lower costs and reduced energy losses, which improves the profitability and efficiency of the hybrid system. The effectiveness of the proposed topology and control methodology is validated using the MATLAB/Simulink software environment. The satisfactory results achieved under various atmospheric conditions and in different operating modes of the hybrid system, confirm the high efficiency of the proposed control strategy.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Growing international concerns about climate change and the ongoing dangers associated with the exploitation of nuclear power generation technology are leading to new advances in electricity generation from renewable resources. Due to their environmental friendliness and sustainability, wind and solar energies have become widespread energy resources. But these resources are intermittent in nature, making it difficult to ensure a stable and continuous energy supply. The problem can be overcome by efficiently integrating local energy storage elements, but their limited life time adds an additional ongoing production cost.

Hybridization of renewable resources, especially if they are complementary in terms of availability, is an adequate solution to the problem of intermittency. Hybridization also reduces the number of power converters, which are typically dedicated to each resource, thus allowing efficient use of the installed converters. In addition, direct grid connection, whilst providing an intelligent energy management system to match production to use, is an appropriate approach to minimize or eliminate storage devices altogether.

A considerable academic literature on renewable power generation (RPG) is mainly devoted to their sizing, reliability, cost analysis, and energy management [1]-[6], whilst others contribute to their modelling and control techniques [7]-[9]. A maximum power point tracking (MPPT) controller is required to make the best use of the available energy. To this end, intensive work has been carried out on MPPT control of photovoltaic and wind energy systems [10]-[15], but most of proposed control methods are based on conventional methods, such as perturbation and observation or incremental conductance algorithms and proportional-integral (PI) controllers. In fact, these systems are nonlinear and the PI controller is designed for linear systems. The high performance of nonlinear controllers compared to conventional controllers has already been reported by several comparative studies [16], [17], and various nonlinear controllers have been

proposed as efficient alternatives to conventional MPPT controls [18]-[22]. On another note, grid codes, such as the FERC standard interconnection agreements for wind and other alternative technologies (order No. 661-A), require that a power factor greater than 0.95 be maintained at the point of interconnection. For this purpose, power factor control for grid-connected RPG systems is of paramount importance [23]-[25].

Against this background, the present work proposes an efficient nonlinear control of a low-cost grid-connected PV-wind hybrid configuration. This paper assumes that the grid connection process, as detailed in [26], [27], has already been done. The proposed hybrid system components and their models are presented in the next section, and on the basis of these models nonlinear control laws are developed in the third section. The results of the simulations undertaken to validate and evaluate the proposed control strategy are presented in the fourth section, and a brief conclusion is given in the last section.

2. SYSTEM ELEMENTS AND THEIR MODELS

The proposed hybrid system configuration is illustrated in Figure 1. Using common electronic power converters, this configuration offers considerable savings in initial and operating costs (less energy loss). In fact, DC/DC and DC/AC converters dedicated to the conversion of photovoltaic (PV) energy are eliminated and the double fed induction generator (DFIG) converters will take care of the conversion of PV energy.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of the proposed hybrid system and control strategy

2.1. Aerodynamic energy conversion

The aerodynamic power, P_{aer} , captured by the turbine used in the proposed system is given by [18]:

$$P_{aer} = \frac{1}{2} C_p(\lambda, \beta) \rho \pi R^2 V_w^3 \quad \left| \quad \begin{aligned} C_p(\lambda, \beta) &= c_1 \left(\frac{c_2}{\lambda_i} - c_3 \beta - c_4 \right) e^{-\frac{c_5}{\lambda_i}} + c_6 \lambda \\ \lambda &= \frac{\Omega_t R}{V_w}; \quad \frac{1}{\lambda_i} = \frac{1}{\lambda + 0.08 \beta} - \frac{0.035}{\beta^3 + 1} \end{aligned} \right. \quad (1)$$

where: C_p is the wind turbine power coefficient; ρ is the air density; R is the blade radius (in metres); V_w is the wind speed (in m/s); Ω_t is the turbine angular speed (in rad/s); λ is the tip speed ratio and β is the blade pitch angle (in degrees). With $c_1=0.5176$; $c_2=116$; $c_3=0.4$; $c_4=5$; $c_5=21$ and $c_6=0.0068$. Figure 2 shows the characteristics of the wind turbine's power coefficient at different values of the blade pitch angle. The pitch control protects the turbine against turbulence and excessive overload, under normal conditions $\beta=0$.

2.2. Photovoltaic energy conversion

The mathematical expressions for the single-diode equivalent circuit of the PV cell are given by [19]:

$$I_{cell} = I_{ph} - I_s \left[e^{\left(\frac{q(V_{cell} + I_{cell}R_s)}{\gamma K T} \right)} - 1 \right] - \frac{V_{cell} + I_{cell}R_s}{R_{sh}} \quad \begin{cases} I_{ph} = \frac{E}{E_{ref}} [I_{sc} + K_i(T - T_{ref})] \\ I_s = I_{rs} \left(\frac{T}{T_{ref}} \right)^3 e^{-\frac{qE_{g0}}{\gamma K} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_{ref}} \right)} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where: I_{cell} is the current crossing the PV cell; V_{cell} is the PV cell voltage; I_{ph} is the photocurrent; I_s , I_{rs} and I_{sc} are the cell saturation current, the reverse saturation current and the short-circuits current; q is the electron charge; R_{sh} and R_s are the intrinsic parallel and series resistors; K is the Boltzmann constant; γ is the diode ideality factor; E is the solar irradiance; E_{ref} is the reference irradiance (1 kW/m²); T is the temperature on absolute scale; T_{ref} is the reference temperature (298,15K); K_i is the short-circuit current temperature coefficient and E_{g0} is the band-gap energy of the cell. Therefore, with a photovoltaic generator (PVG) consisting of N_p strings in parallel, each string consists of N_s cells in series, the expression of the PVG current (I_{pv}) as a function of its voltage (V_{pv}) can be derived as follows:

$$\begin{cases} V_{pv} = N_s V_{cell} \\ I_{pv} = N_p I_{cell} \end{cases} \Rightarrow I_{pv} = N_p I_{ph} - N_p I_s \left[e^{\left(\frac{q N_p V_{pv} + N_s I_{pv} R_s}{\gamma K T N_p N_s} \right)} - 1 \right] - \frac{N_p V_{pv} + N_s I_{pv} R_s}{N_s R_{sh}} \quad (3)$$

In this paper, a PVG made up of seventeen SM55 panels connected in series is considered. Electrical specifications for one panel are given in [21]. The Power-Voltage characteristics of the PVG under solar irradiance change are shown in Figure 3. The coordinates of the maximum power points shown in the zoomed-in parts of Figures 2 and 3 will be used to verify the simulation results.

Figure 2. $C_p(\lambda)$ characteristics for different values of β

Figure 3. Power characteristics of the GPV

2.3. State space representation

All measured 3-phase quantities are transformed into the stator-flux oriented dq-reference frame as shown in Figure 1. The DC-bus voltage, which is also the PVG voltage (V_{pv}), is governed by the following equation:

$$\frac{dV_{pv}}{dt} = \frac{1}{C} (K_{dg} I_{dg} + K_{qg} I_{qg} + I_{pv} - I_{rc}) \quad (4)$$

where C is the DC-bus capacitor; I_{rc} is the DC-current absorbed by the rotor side converter (RSC); I_{dg} and I_{qg} are the d-axis and q-axis components of the current absorbed by the grid side converter (GSC); K_{dg} and K_{qg} are the GSC control signal components in d-q frame.

In the synchronous dq-frame, the stator flux vector is aligned on the d-axis. Assuming that the stator flux magnitude is constant and the small drop in the stator resistance voltage is negligible, the stator voltage vector is also considered practically aligned on the q-axis of the dq-frame [27]-[29]. According to (4) and [18] an overall state space representation of the hybrid system under consideration is given by:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dI_{dr}}{dt} = \omega_r I_{qr} - \frac{R_r}{L_r \sigma} I_{dr} + \frac{V_{pv}}{L_r \sigma} K_{dr} \\ \frac{dI_{qr}}{dt} = -\omega_r I_{dr} - \frac{\omega_r M}{\omega_s L_s L_r \sigma} V_s - \frac{R_r}{L_r \sigma} I_{qr} + \frac{V_{pv}}{L_r \sigma} K_{qr} \\ \frac{dI_{dg}}{dt} = \omega_s I_{qg} - \frac{R_f}{L_f} I_{dg} - \frac{V_{pv}}{L_f} K_{dg} \\ \frac{dI_{qg}}{dt} = -\omega_s I_{dg} - \frac{R_f}{L_f} I_{qg} + \frac{V_g}{L_f} - \frac{V_{pv}}{L_f} K_{qg} \\ \frac{dV_{pv}}{dt} = \frac{1}{C} (K_{dg} I_{dg} + K_{qg} I_{qg} + I_{pv} - I_{rc}) \end{cases} \quad \begin{cases} \omega_s = \frac{d\theta_s}{dt} \\ \omega_r = \frac{d\theta_r}{dt} = \omega_s - p\Omega_r \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where I_{dr} and I_{qr} are the rotor current components; L_s and L_r are the stator and rotor inductances; R_r is the resistance of rotor windings; $\theta_s(\theta_r)$ are the angular position of the d-q frame with respect to the reference frame attached to the stator (rotor); M is the stator-rotor magnetizing inductance; σ is the leakage coefficient ($\sigma = 1 - M^2/L_s L_r$); K_{dr} and K_{qr} are the RSC control signal components; R_f and L_f are the resistance and the inductance of the L-filter; V_s is the q-axis component of the stator voltage; V_g is the quadrature component of the transformer (T_r) secondary voltage, see Figure 1, with $V_g = mV_s$; m is the transformation ratio of T_r . The electromagnetic torque is expressed in the synchronous frame as:

$$T_{em} = -p \frac{M}{L_s} \varphi_s I_{qr} \quad (6)$$

where p is the number of pole pairs per phase in the DFIG stator windings; φ_s is the d-axis component of the stator flux.

3. DESIGN OF HYBRID SYSTEM CONTROLLERS

The grid voltage is assumed to be stable, and the stator flux is estimated as:

$$\hat{\varphi}_{s_i} = \int (v_{s_i} - R_s i_{s_i}) dt; \quad i \in \{a, b, c\} \quad (7)$$

The angular frequency (ω_s) and the phase angle (θ_s) of the synchronous d-q frame are generated using a three-phase phase-locked loop (PLL), as shown in Figure 4 [18], [21].

Figure 4. Block diagram of the PLL

The RSC controller is designed to track the maximum power point (MPP) of the wind turbine and to inject the stator power with near unity power factor (UPF). The GSC controller is designed to track the MPP of the PVG and to maintain the reactive power injected by the GSC close to zero in Figure 1.

3.1. Designation of the hybrid system outputs and their references

The DFIG rotor dynamics obey Newton's second law for rotational dynamics, thus:

$$J \frac{d\Omega_r}{dt} = T_{a/r} + T_{em} - F\Omega_r \quad (8)$$

where, J and F are the total inertia and total viscosity coefficient (turbine and DFIG), $T_{a/r}$ is the aerodynamic torque applied to DFIG rotor, T_{em} is the algebraic value of the DFIG electromagnetic torque and Ω_r its rotor speed. Operating the wind turbine at the maximum power point (i.e. $\lambda = \lambda_{opt}$ and $C_p = C_{p,max}$) means that:

$$P_{aer} = P_{aer,max} \stackrel{(1)}{\Rightarrow} P_{aer,max} = \frac{1}{2} C_{p,max} \rho \pi R^2 (V_w)^3 = \frac{1}{2} C_{p,max} \rho \pi R^2 \left(\frac{\Omega_t R}{\lambda_{opt}} \right)^3 \quad (9)$$

Then, the optimal aerodynamic torque, $T_{a/r,opt}$, is such that:

$$T_{a/r_opt} = \frac{P_{aermax}}{\Omega_r} \xrightarrow{(\Omega_r=G\Omega_t)} T_{a/r_opt} = K_{opt}\Omega_r^2 \tag{10}$$

where $K_{opt} = \frac{\rho\pi R^5 C_{p_max}}{2G^3\lambda_{opt}^3}$; G is the gearbox ratio and Ω_r is the DFIG rotor speed. The optimal electromagnetic torque (T_{em_opt}) and then the reference of the first output (q-axis rotor current; I_{qr}) are derived as:

$$\stackrel{(8)}{\Rightarrow} T_{em_opt} = F\Omega_r - T_{a/r_opt} \tag{11}$$

$$\stackrel{(6)\&(10)}{\Rightarrow} I_{qrref} = \frac{L_s}{pM\phi_s} (K_{opt}\Omega_r^2 - F\Omega_r) \Rightarrow \frac{dI_{qrref}}{dt} = \frac{L_s}{pM\phi_s} \frac{d\Omega_r}{dt} (2K_{opt}\Omega_r - F) \tag{12}$$

The reactive powers are expressed as a function of I_{dr} and I_{dg} (second and third outputs) as [18]:

$$\begin{cases} Q_s = \frac{V_s^2}{\omega_s L_s} - \frac{MV_s}{L_s} I_{dr} \\ Q_g = V_g I_{dg} \end{cases} \tag{13}$$

where Q_s is the reactive power injected by the DFIG stator; Q_g is the reactive powers injected by the GSC. In order to operate the hybrid system at or near UPF, the references of the direct currents are derived as:

$$\begin{cases} Q_{s_opt} = \frac{V_s^2}{\omega_s L_s} - \frac{MV_s}{L_s} I_{drref} = 0 \\ Q_{g_opt} = V_g I_{dgref} = 0 \end{cases} \Rightarrow \begin{cases} I_{drref} = \frac{V_s}{M\omega_s} \\ I_{dgref} = 0 \end{cases} \& \left| \frac{dI_{drref}}{dt} = \frac{dI_{dgref}}{dt} = 0 \right. \tag{14}$$

Since the PVG characteristics have a single extremum, as shown in Figure 3, the derivative of the PVG power with respect to its voltage ($\frac{\partial P_{pv}}{\partial V_{pv}}$) was chosen as the fourth output of the system with a reference value of zero:

$$\left(\frac{\partial P_{pv}}{\partial V_{pv}} \right)_{ref} = 0 \tag{15}$$

3.2. Elaboration of RSC control laws

Let us define the first error ε_1 and a first lyapunov function candidate (LFC) \mathcal{V}_1 as:

$$\varepsilon_1 = I_{qr} - I_{qrref}; \quad \mathcal{V}_1 = \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon_1^2 + \frac{1}{2} \sigma_1^2 \tag{16}$$

where $\sigma_1 = c_{1i} \int_0^t \varepsilon_1(\tau) d\tau$, c_{1i} is the design parameter of the integral action. \mathcal{V}_1 time-derivative is as:

$$\frac{d\mathcal{V}_1}{dt} = \varepsilon_1 \left(\frac{d\varepsilon_1}{dt} + c_{1i}\sigma_1 \right) \stackrel{(5)}{\Rightarrow} \frac{d\mathcal{V}_1}{dt} = \varepsilon_1 \left(c_{1i}\sigma_1 - \omega_r I_{dr} - \frac{\omega_r MV_s}{\omega_s L_s L_r \sigma} - \frac{R_r}{L_r \sigma} I_{qr} + \frac{K_{qr} V_{pv}}{L_r \sigma} - \frac{dI_{qrref}}{dt} \right) \tag{17}$$

The q-axis component of RSC control signal, K_{qr} , is chosen as:

$$K_{qr} = \frac{L_r \sigma}{V_{pv}} \left(-c_{1i}\varepsilon_1 - c_{1i}\sigma_1 + \omega_r I_{dr} + \frac{R_r}{L_r \sigma} I_{qr} + \frac{\omega_r MV_s}{\omega_s L_s L_r \sigma} + \frac{dI_{qrref}}{dt} \right) \tag{18}$$

where c_1 is a strictly positive design parameter. \mathcal{V}_1 time derivative of the closed-loop system becomes:

$$\frac{d\mathcal{V}_1}{dt} = -c_1 \varepsilon_1^2 \tag{19}$$

Similarly, the error between I_{dr} and its desired value, and a second LFC are defined as follows:

$$\varepsilon_2 = I_{dr} - I_{drref}; \quad \mathcal{V}_2 = \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon_2^2 + \frac{1}{2} \sigma_2^2 \tag{20}$$

where $\sigma_2 = c_{2i} \int_0^t \varepsilon_2(\tau) d\tau$, c_{2i} is the design parameter of the integral action. \mathcal{V}_2 time-derivative is as:

$$\frac{dV_2}{dt} = \varepsilon_2 \left(\frac{d\varepsilon_2}{dt} + c_{2i}\sigma_2 \right) \stackrel{(5)}{\Rightarrow} \frac{dV_2}{dt} = \varepsilon_2 (\omega_r I_{qr} - \frac{R_r}{L_r \sigma} I_{dr} + \frac{V_{pv}}{L_r \sigma} K_{dr} + c_{2i}\sigma_2 - \frac{dI_{drref}}{dt}) \quad (21)$$

Then, the d-axis component of RSC control signal is chosen such that:

$$K_{dr} = \frac{L_r \sigma}{V_{pv}} (-c_2 \varepsilon_2 - c_{2i} \sigma_2 + \frac{R_r}{L_r \sigma} I_{dr} - \omega_r I_{qr}) \quad (22)$$

where c_2 is a strictly positive design parameter. With the above choice, V_2 time derivative becomes:

$$\frac{dV_2}{dt} = -c_2 \varepsilon_2^2 \quad (23)$$

3.3. Elaboration of GSC control laws

The error ε_3 , between I_{dg} and its desired value, and a third LFC are defined as:

$$\varepsilon_3 = I_{dg} - I_{dgref}; \quad V_3 = \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon_3^2 + \frac{1}{2} \sigma_3^2 \quad (24)$$

where $\sigma_3 = c_{3i} \int_0^t \varepsilon_3(\tau) d\tau$; c_{3i} is the design parameter of the integral action. So, V_3 time-derivative is as:

$$\frac{dV_3}{dt} = \varepsilon_3 \left(\frac{d\varepsilon_3}{dt} + c_{3i}\sigma_3 \right) \stackrel{(5)}{\Rightarrow} \frac{dV_3}{dt} = \varepsilon_3 (\omega_s I_{qg} - \frac{R_f}{L_f} I_{dg} - \frac{V_{pv}}{L_f} K_{dg} + c_{3i}\sigma_3) \quad (25)$$

Then, the d-axis component of GSC control signal is chosen as:

$$A_1 K_{dg} + A_2 K_{qg} = B_1 \quad (26)$$

where: $A_1 = \frac{V_{pv}}{L_f}$; $A_2 = 0$; $B_1 = c_3 \varepsilon_3 + c_{3i} \sigma_3 + \omega_s I_{qg} - \frac{R_f}{L_f} I_{dg}$; with c_3 is a strictly positive design parameter.

The above choice guarantees the closed-loop negativity of the V_3 time-derivative, which would become:

$$\frac{dV_3}{dt} = -c_3 \varepsilon_3^2 \quad (27)$$

The PV-MPPT error ε_4 and a fourth LFC, V_4 , are defined as:

$$\varepsilon_4 = \frac{\partial P_{pv}}{\partial V_{pv}} - \left(\frac{\partial P_{pv}}{\partial V_{pv}} \right)_{ref} = \frac{\partial P_{pv}}{\partial V_{pv}} = I_{pv} + V_{pv} \frac{\partial I_{pv}}{\partial V_{pv}}; \quad V_4 = \frac{1}{2} \varepsilon_4^2 + \frac{1}{2} \sigma_4^2 \quad (28)$$

where $\sigma_4 = c_{4i} \int_0^t \varepsilon_4(\tau) d\tau$; c_{4i} is the integral action design parameter. ε_4 derivative can be formulated as:

$$\frac{d\varepsilon_4}{dt} = f \frac{dV_{pv}}{dt} = \frac{f}{c} (K_{dg} I_{dg} + K_{qg} I_{qg} + I_{pv} - I_{rc}) \quad (29)$$

where $f = V_{pv} \frac{\partial^2 I_{pv}}{\partial V_{pv}^2} + 2 \frac{\partial I_{pv}}{\partial V_{pv}}$. The time-derivative of V_4 is deduced as

$$\frac{dV_4}{dt} = \varepsilon_4 \left(\frac{d\varepsilon_4}{dt} + c_{4i}\sigma_4 \right) = \varepsilon_4 \left(\frac{f}{c} (K_{dg} I_{dg} + K_{qg} I_{qg} + I_{pv} - I_{rc}) + c_{4i}\sigma_4 \right) \quad (30)$$

Then, K_{dg} and K_{qg} are chosen in such a way that they satisfy:

$$A_3 K_{dg} + A_4 K_{qg} = B_2 \quad (31)$$

where: $A_3 = \frac{f}{c} I_{dg}$; $A_4 = \frac{f}{c} I_{qg}$; $B_2 = -c_4 \varepsilon_4 - c_{4i} \sigma_4 + \frac{f}{c} (I_{rc} - I_{pv})$ and c_4 is a strictly positive design parameter. Subsequently, the V_4 time-derivative of the closed-loop system becomes:

$$\frac{dV_4}{dt} = -c_4 \varepsilon_4^2 \quad (32)$$

Then, the GSC control signals, K_{dg} and K_{qg} , are calculated using (26) and (31):

$$\begin{bmatrix} K_{dg} \\ K_{qg} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_1 & A_2 \\ A_3 & A_4 \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} B_1 \\ B_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (33)$$

3.4. Overall stability analysis

Let us define an overall Lyapunov function candidate \mathcal{V}_T such as:

$$\mathcal{V}_T = \sum_{i=1}^4 \mathcal{V}_i = \sum_{i=1}^4 \frac{\epsilon_i^2}{2} + \sum_{i=1}^4 \frac{\sigma_i^2}{2} \tag{34}$$

According to (19) ,(23), (27) and (32), \mathcal{V}_T time-derivative of the closed-loop system is:

$$\frac{d\mathcal{V}_T}{dt} = \sum_{i=1}^4 \frac{d\mathcal{V}_i}{dt} = - \sum_{i=1}^4 c_i \epsilon_i^2 \tag{35}$$

Thus, \mathcal{V}_T is a positive definite function and has a negative definite derivative, therefore the tracking errors are asymptotically stable and converge to zero in Lyapunov's approach.

4. SIMULATION RESULTS

The closed-loop hybrid system is modeled in MATLAB-Simulink software in order to assess the performance of the designed controllers. The main parameters used for the simulation are summarized in Table 1. Figure 5 shows Matlab/Simulink diagram for the hybrid system. The solar radiation and wind velocity profiles shown in Figure 6 are used to perform this assessment.

Figure 5. Matlab/Simulink diagram for the hybrid system

Table 1. Parameters of controlled system

				Hybrid system	
DFIG rated power	$P_n=1kW$	Blade radius	$R=0.9 m$	Rotor resistance	$R_r=0.88\Omega$
Line to line voltage	$U_s=190V$	Viscous coefficient	$F=64 \times 10^{-2} Nms/rad$	Stator resistance	$R_s=1.01\Omega$
DFIG pole pair number	$p=3$	Gearbox ratio	$G=1.3$	Filter inductance	$L_f=12.6 mH$
Maximal power coefficient	$C_{p,max}=4.8$	Switching frequency	$f_s=10kHz$	Mutual inductance	$M=90.1 mH$
Air density	$\rho=1.22kg/m^3$	DC-bus capacitor	$C=100\mu F$	Rotor inductance	$L_r=93.1 mH$
Optimal Tip speed ratio	$\lambda_{opt}=8.13$	Filter resistance	$R_f=0.5655\Omega$	Stator inductance	$L_s=93.1 mH$
				Controllers	
				$c_1=7 \times 10^5$;	$c_{1i}=7 \times 10^3$;
				$c_2=6 \times 10^5$;	$c_{2i}=7 \times 10^2$;
				$c_3=36 \times 10^4$;	$c_{3i}=20 \times 10^5$;
				$c_4=10^5$;	$c_{4i}=50 \times 10^5$

A PI controller has been proposed in [29] for controlling the same hybrid system proposed in this paper and the MPPT algorithm "perturbe and observe" (including the PVG power limitation to avoid GSC overload) was used to adjust the PVG voltage. In order to provide a good idea of the proposed control performance, the simulation results obtained using the control strategy proposed in [29] are also presented (as the algorithm for tracking the maximum power of the turbine has not been specified in [29], the q-axis rotor current reference established in this paper has been used in order to provide MPPT control of the wind turbine).

Figure 6. Environmental conditions, (a) solar radiation profile, (b) wind velocity profile

The first simulation result, Figure 7, clearly shows that the PLL has successfully met its objective (q-axis stator flux is almost zero), and that its outputs are more accurate when used with the integral backstepping control. Figure 8 shows that the d-axis component of the stator voltage (which has been neglected in the design of the controllers) is indeed practically zero; its value does not exceed 0.2V with the proposed controller and $\pm 0.6V$ with the PI controller. Figure 9 shows the tracking efficiency of the q-axis rotor current reference provided by the proposed RSC controller, which results in very good tracking performance of the optimal electromagnetic torque, as shown in Figure 10. Figure 11 shows that the power coefficient of the wind turbine has been kept close to its maximum value regardless of variations in wind speed. Figure 12 shows that the d-axis rotor current was kept close to its reference value (with a tracking error of less than 0.5A) and hence the stator reactive power was kept close to zero, as shown in Figure 13. Moreover, the proposed GSC controller has been proven more efficient in controlling the reactive power injected by the GSC close to zero, as shown in Figure 14.

Figure 7. DFIG stator flux

Figure 8. DFIG stator voltage

Figure 9. q-axis rotor current

Figure 10. DFIG electromagnetic torque

The total injected power, shown in Figure 15, reveals that the total reactive power is near zero and the active power injected using the proposed controller is greater than that generated using the PI controller. The wind speed profile in Figure 6 was used to evaluate the hybrid system during different operating modes of the DFIG, as can be seen in Figure 16. In the sub-synchronous mode, the power of the PVG is routed through both the GSC and the RSC. Therefore, the active power injected by the GSC becomes lower than that produced by the PVG, as can be seen in the zoomed-in portion of Figure 14.

Figure 11. Evolution of the power coefficient

Figure 12. d-axis rotor current

Figure 13. Stator active and reactive powers

Figure 14. Real and reactive powers injected via GSC

Figure 15. Total injected powers

Figure 16. DFIG rotor speed

Figures 17 and 18 show that the PVG voltage, and the PV power generated correspond very precisely to the MPP coordinates of the PVG shown in Figure 3. Figure 19 illustrates that the total current injected using the proposed controller exhibits less fluctuations than that obtained using the PI controller, and that the power factor has been maintained at unity independently of the rotor current behaviour shown in Figure 20.

Figure 17. DC-bus voltage behaviour

Figure 18. PV power supplied by the PVG

Figure 19. UPF operation, (a) total current injected into one grid phase, (b) zoomed-in portions of

Figure 20. Behaviour of rotor currents, (a) integral backstepping control, (b) PI control

5. CONCLUSION

A nonlinear control strategy for a grid-connected PV-wind hybrid system has been presented. The main control objectives are to guarantee the maximum extraction of locally available renewable energy and to operate the grid-connected hybrid system near unity power factor. The control laws have been developed in the stator-flux oriented reference frame on the basis of Lyapunov's stability theory. The soundness of the proposed control strategy has been confirmed by numerical simulations and its performance was compared to that obtained with a previously proposed one. The results obtained highlight the performance of the proposed nonlinear controller. Future work will concentrate on experimental testing of the proposed control strategy, as well as on improving the control of other renewable energy systems.

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